

CHANGE IN DEFORMATION/FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF INTERFACE-CONTROLLED HAP/PLLA COMPOSITES BY HYDROLYSIS

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SUMMARY

The interface-control for HAp/PLLA composite was tried in order to improve the bonding strength. The effects of interface control on deformation and fracture properties of HAp/PLLA composites were evaluated using three-point bending tests. The effect of interface control on hydrolysis behavior was discussed from the viewpoint of interfacial mesoscopic structures.

Keywords: Interface-controlled HAp/PLLA Composite, Scaffold Material, Bone Regeneration, Deformation/Fracture Behavior, Hydrolysis

INTRODUCTION

In the traditional bone filling surgery, biocompatible substitute materials are implanted into bone defects. In this case, the re-implantation of substitute materials is inevitable owing to the age-related deterioration. In addition, the surrounding bone is sometimes absorbed owing to the stress-shielding phenomenon induced by the extremely high stiffness of substitute materials in comparison with surrounding bone [1]. Therefore, the development of the bone regeneration technique is expected utilizing porous scaffold materials as bone substitutes and cellular bone formation activities [2-4]. Here, the complete bone regeneration will be achieved by hydrolytic resorption of scaffold materials and replacement into newly formed bone. The main requirements for scaffold materials are biocompatibility, bone-conductivity, biodegradability, and comparable stiffness and strength to healthy bone. Therefore, the biocompatible materials composed of hydroxyapatite (HAp) particles and poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) are one of the most promising candidates as scaffold materials, owing to the bone-conductivity of HAp and the biodegradability of PLLA [5-8]. However, the poor fracture properties, mainly caused by the weak interface [6,8], are one of the factors limiting their practical application.

In this study, the interface control was tried by surface treatment of HAp particles using natural-derived biocompatible polymers, in order to improve the bonding strength. The effect of interface control on deformation and fracture properties of HAp/PLLA composites was evaluated using three-point bending tests. The effect of interface control

on hydrolysis behavior was discussed from the viewpoint of interfacial mesoscopic structures.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material Preparation

The HAp particles (Eccera, Co. Ltd., $\phi = 0.1$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$) and PLLA (API, Co. Ltd., initial viscosity average molecular weight: 2×10^5) were used in this study. As the surface treatment polymers, pectin (Nakarai Tesque, Inc.) and chitosan (Nakarai Tesque, Inc.) were selected in consideration with biological affinity. The neat PLLA films as the control material and HAp/PLLA films using untreated, pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp particles were prepared by precipitation and following melt-pressing [9]. The weight fraction of HAp particles was 20 wt% (9.1 vol%). Prepared materials were immersed into phosphate buffer solution (PBS, $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH 7.4) as pseudo bio-environment for 0-24 weeks.

Testing Procedure

Three point bending tests were carried out in accordance with JIS K 7171 [10] using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu, Autograph AG 50-kNG) with a load cell of 50 N in capacity. Specimens of 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width and 0.5 mm in nominal thickness were prepared. The loading span was 20 mm. The strain rate at tensile side specimen surface was 1 %/min (crosshead speed: 1.3 mm/min). The fracture surfaces were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL, Ltd., JSM-5410LS) and a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) (Hitachi, Ltd., S-4500).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of Bending Tests

Figure 1 shows the change in bending elastic modulus with hydrolysis. The initial bending moduli of untreated, pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp/PLLAs were about 10 %, 33 % and 30 % higher than that of neat PLLA, respectively. The decrease in elastic moduli was evident in the early stage of hydrolytic resorption, and then saturated. This tendency was markedly in untreated HAp/PLLA.

Figure 2 shows the change in bending strength with hydrolysis. The initial bending strength of untreated HAp/PLLA was about 50 % of that of neat PLLA. The relative decrease of elastic modulus and strength with hydrolysis in untreated HAp/PLLA was higher than that in neat PLLA. On the other hand, interface-controlled HAp/PLLAs maintained almost the same level as neat PLLA, regardless of immersion time.

Fracture Surfaces

Figure 3 indicates the typical fracture surface of untreated HAp/PLLA. Even without hydrolysis, the surface of untreated HAp particles was mostly exposed owing to

Figure 1. Change in bending moduli of neat PLLA and HAp/PLLAs with hydrolysis.

Figure 2. Change in bending strength of neat PLLA and HAp/PLLAs with hydrolysis.

interfacial debonding. This means that the interface between untreated HAp particles and surrounding PLLA matrix was intrinsically weak. The gap at debonded interface expanded with increasing immersion time. Since this gap was induced by hydrolysis of PLLA matrix, PLLA matrix adjacent to debonded interface was selectively degraded by localized water diffusion into debonded interface.

Figures 4 and 5 indicate the typical fracture surfaces of pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp/PLLAs, respectively. Here, the interface bonding between HAp particles and PLLA matrix was much improved. Thus, the interfacial bonding condition between HAp particles and PLLA matrix was successfully improved by surface treatment of

(a) Without hydrolysis

(b) After 12-week hydrolysis

Figure 3. Fracture surfaces of untreated HAp/PLLA.

(a) Without hydrolysis

(b) After 12-week hydrolysis

Figure 4. Fracture surfaces of pectin-treated HAp/PLLA.

(a) Without hydrolysis

(b) After 12-week hydrolysis

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces of chitosan-treated HAp/PLLA.

HAp particles using pectin or chitosan. Even after 12-week immersion, interface bonding between HAp particles and PLLA was still maintained. This suggests that interface control suppressed water diffusion and consequent hydrolytic resorption by the improvement of interfacial bonding condition. In addition, the drawn PLLA adhesive was stuck on the HAp particles and showed larger plastic deformation after hydrolysis. Thus, it is suggested that the degradation speed of PLLA matrix adjacent to bonded interface was comparable to that of PLLA matrix away from interface in interface-controlled HAp/PLLAs, from the mesomechanical viewpoint. However, the debonded interface was also partially observed even for interface-controlled HAp/PLLAs. This suggests that the efficiency of interface control employed in this study was not perfect.

Effect of Interface Control on Hydrolysis Behavior

As mentioned above, PLLA matrix adjacent to debonded interface was locally and selectively degraded in untreated HAp/PLLA. This means that the water diffused at debonded interface selectively. It is suggested that the decrease in stress transfer ability between untreated HAp particles and PLLA matrix by the selective interfacial degradation induced the higher degradation speed of mechanical properties in untreated HAp/PLLA.

On the other hand, the degradation speed of PLLA matrix adjacent to bonded interface was suggested to be comparable to that of PLLA matrix away from interface in interface-controlled HAp/PLLAs. This means that interface control suppressed water diffusion by the improvement of interfacial bonding condition. Thus, it is suggested that the PLLA matrix surrounding HAp particles could deform plastically, resulting in improvement of bending strength of HAp/PLLAs by interface control.

However, as mentioned in the previous section, the efficiency of interface control employed in this study was still not perfect. Thus, it is suggested that the increase in the efficiency of interface control potentially improves elastic moduli and strength of HAp/PLLAs. In addition, the control of the degradation speed could be designed by the change in the efficiency of interface control, on the basis of further fundamental understanding of the effect of the efficiency of interface control on the hydrolytic resorption behavior of HAp/PLLAs.

Modelling of Change in Elastic Modulus with Hydrolysis

In order to optimise the microscopic structure of HAp/PLLA as scaffold, it is necessary to predict the change in the deformation/fracture properties of HAp/PLLA in living body precisely. Particularly, the difference in elastic modulus between transplanted portion and surrounding healthy bone is one of the most important parameters, because it has possibility to induce stress-shielding phenomenon and damage of surrounding bone. Thus, we tried modelling of change in elastic modulus with hydrolysis using a rule of mixture for particle-dispersed composites shown below [11].

$$E_c = \frac{E_m + (E_p - E_m)V_p^{2/3}}{E_m + (E_p - E_m)V_p^{2/3}(1 - V_p^{1/3})} E_m \quad (1)$$

Here, E and V are elastic modulus and volume fraction, and subscript characters (p, m and c) means particle, matrix and composite, respectively. This rule of mixture is formed under the assumptions, such as perfect interfacial bonding, uniform dispersion of particles, the agreement of Poisson's ratio between particles and matrix, the disregard of complex stress distribution at interface, and so on.

First, the decreasing behavior of elastic modulus for neat PLLA was categorised into the early stage (Region A: immersion time, $t < 4$ [week]) and the latter stager (Region B: $t > 4$ [week]). In this study, it was linearly approximated as $E_m(t) = 3.00 (1 - 0.0667 t)$ [GPa] and $E_m(t) = 2.28 (1 - 0.00877 t)$ [GPa] for Regions A and B, respectively. The employed elastic modulus of HAp particles, E_p , is 110 [GPa] [12].

Figure 6. Prediction for change in elastic moduli of HAp /PLLAs with hydrolysis.

Secondly, HAp particles, which are initially debonded, were assumed to act as defects. In this study, the ratio of initially debonded HAp particles, $\alpha (=V_{\text{defect}}/V_p)$, was defined. In this case, the volume fraction of HAp particles which act as reinforcement, $V_{\text{efficient}}$, is expressed as $(1-\alpha)V_p$. In this study, $\alpha_{\text{untreated}}$ was assumed as 0.95 for untreated HAp/PLLA. On the other hand, α_{treated} was assumed as 0.60 for pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp/PLLAs.

Then, the volume expansion ratio of gaps surrounding debonded HAp particles, $\beta(t)$, was defined. In this study, $\beta(t)$ was evaluated as 1.00 and 0.144 $t-0.604$ for Regions A and B, respectively, from typical fracture surfaces by image processing. Here, the volume fraction of defects after t week immersion, $V_{\text{defect}}(t)$, is expressed as $\alpha\beta(t)V_p$. Thus, the elastic modulus of PLLA with defects of $V_{\text{defect}}(t)$, $E_{m,\text{defect}}(t)$, can be expressed as follows.

$$E_{m,\text{defect}}(t) = \frac{1 - V_{\text{defect}}(t)^{2/3}}{1 - V_{\text{defect}}(t)^{2/3} [1 - V_{\text{defect}}(t)^{1/3}]} E_m(t) \quad (2)$$

When HAp/PLLAs were regarded as composite materials composed of PLLA with defects of $V_{\text{defect}}(t)$ and HAp particles of $V_{\text{efficient}}$, the elastic modulus of HAp/PLLAs can be expressed as follows.

$$E_c(t) = \frac{[E_{m,\text{defect}}(t) + (E_p - E_{m,\text{defect}}(t))V_{\text{efficient}}^{2/3}]E_{m,\text{defect}}(t)}{E_{m,\text{defect}}(t) + [E_p - E_{m,\text{defect}}(t)]V_{\text{efficient}}^{2/3} [1 - V_{\text{efficient}}^{1/3}]} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6 shows the change in elastic moduli with hydrolysis predicted by Equation (3). The prediction of change in elastic moduli considering the effect of change in interfacial microstructure agrees with experimental results qualitatively. Therefore, it is suggested that the decrease in elastic moduli of HAp/PLLAs after long-term hydrolysis under the

bio-environment is mainly governed by the hydrolytic deterioration of PLLA matrix and the change in interfacial microstructure.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effect of interface control on deformation and fracture properties of HAp/PLLA composites was evaluated using three-point bending tests. The effect of interface control on hydrolysis behavior was discussed from the viewpoint of interfacial mesoscopic structures. The results are summarized as follows.

- (1) The bending strength of untreated HAp/PLLA was about 50 % of that of neat PLLA. On the other hand, pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp/PLLAs have almost the same level of bending strength as neat PLLA.
- (2) The interfacial bonding strength was successfully improved by the surface treatment of HAp particles using pectin or chitosan.
- (3) The relative decrease of bending elastic modulus and bending strength with hydrolytic resorption in untreated HAp/PLLA were higher than those in neat PLLA. On the other hand, the relative decrease of bending elastic moduli and bending strength with hydrolytic resorption in pectin-treated and chitosan-treated HAp/PLLAs were comparable to those of neat PLLA.
- (4) It is suggested that interface control suppressed water diffusion by the improvement of interfacial bonding condition.
- (5) It is suggested that the increase in the efficiency of interface control potentially improves elastic moduli and strength of HAp/PLLA composites.
- (6) The prediction of change in elastic moduli considering the effect of change in interfacial microstructure agrees with experimental results qualitatively. It is suggested that the decrease in elastic moduli of HAp/PLLAs after long-term hydrolysis under the biological environment is mainly governed by the hydrolytic deterioration of PLLA matrix and the change in interfacial microstructure.

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References

1. G. Ryan, A. Pandit and D.P. Apatsidis, *Biomaterials*, **27** (2006) 2651.
2. R. Langer and J.P. Vacanti, *Science*, **260** (1993) 920.
3. M. Kellomäki, H. Niiranen, K. Puumanen, N. Ashammakhi, T. Waris and P. Törmälä, *Biomaterials*, **21** (2000) 2495.
4. T. Adachi, Y. Osako, M. Tanaka, M. Hojo, S.J. Hollister, *Biomaterials*, **27** (2006) 3964.

5. N. Ignjatović, S. Tomić, M. Dakić, M. Miljković, M. Plavšić and D. Uskoković, *Biomaterials*, **20** (1999) 809.
6. Y. Shikinami and M. Okuno, *Biomaterials*, **20** (1999) 859.
7. G. Wei and P.X. Ma, *Biomaterials*, **25** (2004), 4749.
8. M. Todo, S.D. Park, K. Arakawa and Y. Takenoshita, *Composites, A*, **37** (2006) 2221.
9. T. Nishino, M. Kotera, M. Sugihara, H. Tanaka, M. Tanaka, T. Adachi and M. Hojo, *Polymers Preprints, Japan*, **56** (2007) 2216 (in Japanese).
10. JIS K 7171, *Plastics-Determination of flexural properties*, (1994).
11. R. M. Jones, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, (1998), TAYLOR and FRANCIS.
12. S. Ramesh, C. Y. Tan, I. Sopyan, M. Hamdi and W. D. Teng, *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials*, **8** (2007) 124.